

DESCRIPTION OF OBJECTIVE AND SUBJECTIVE FACTORS OF DEVELOPING YOUTH ECONOMIC ACTIVITY ON THE BASIS OF HEALTHY ETHICAL-ECONOMIC COMPETITION

Bakhtiyor Khamitovich Talipov

Senior Lecturer at the Fergana Branch
of TATU, Ph.D. in Philosophy

ORCID ID: 0009-0002-9430-746X

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Abstract: The article studies the theoretical and methodological foundations of the development of youth economic activity in New Uzbekistan, the deterministic foundations of the development of youth economic activity in New Uzbekistan based on a culture of healthy competition, and the prospects for the development of youth economic activity in New Uzbekistan based on a culture of healthy competition. The deterministic foundations of the development of youth economic activity in New Uzbekistan based on a culture of healthy competition are also analyzed.

Key words: youth economic activity, social laws, tradition and modernity, comparative analysis, analysis and synthesis, systematic and functional, deterministic basis, culture of healthy competition.

INTRODUCTION

One of the primary tasks in shaping a new society is to economically activate the youth, transform them into owners of the skills and potential necessary for societal development, and raise the level of labor skills to a level capable of utilizing new technologies. Therefore, investing in human interests and creating a class of property owners has become a priority of the new socio-economic policy of Uzbekistan. The provision of economic freedom, the protection of entrepreneurship and business by the state, and its legal and regulatory foundation naturally provide a strong impulse for the transformation of moral and cultural values.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODS

The economic activity of the youth has been reflected in the scientific observations of F. Primov, Y. Ernazarova, Sh. Quvondiqov, J. Mavlyanov, and Sh. Azamatov. Researchers in the CIS countries such as G.P. Voshanova, G.S. Godzina, L.G. Golovach, V.YE. Savchenko, D. Sakhal, D.I. Kokurin, O.A. Latukha, A.D. Sheremet, and Y.V. Sherbinina have also conducted scientific studies. These researchers have focused on the changes in post-totalitarian socio-economic life, the processes of systemic transformation, the realization of economic rights and freedoms on national soil, the development of business and entrepreneurship,

and issues related to innovations in scientific technology and societal development. The theoretical and social-philosophical conclusions, analytical methods, and sociometric observations of these scholars are significant for our research as well. From foreign scholars, E. Porter, E. Maykl, K.Y. Totyev, A.Y. Yudanov, G.L. Azoyev, A.P. Gradov, M.V. Konotopov, and R.A. Fatkhutdinov have studied various issues in the improvement of competition processes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There are objective and subjective factors that increase the economic activity of the youth. The objective factor includes the regulatory documents adopted by state bodies, the control established in the country over their compliance, and the activities of various public organizations. The control over the enforcement of laws by the state ensures strict adherence to the laws and helps form the understanding that voluntary compliance with them is a necessary and appropriate goal. The subjective factors of increasing the economic activity of the youth are as follows: scientific-technical and technological progress, organizing labor on a scientific basis, labor standardization and motivation, and the use of new technologies in small business and private entrepreneurship. The success of the youth and the achievements of the transitional period are interrelated. The opportunities created by the new economic environment help develop initiative, creativity, and adaptability among the youth. However, there are also risks that previous generations did not face, such as deepening inequality, unemployment, drug addiction, and others. In other words, while the transitional period opens up vast opportunities for the youth, it also brings along various challenges.

The youth's sense of ownership over the means of production and the results of production signals the creation of favorable conditions for future entrepreneurial activities. A number of competitive selection processes are being organized to encourage the growth of youth's economic activity and foster a fair attitude toward labor.

Currently, the issues of modeling the economic activity of the youth are becoming significant research objects in various social, political, and humanitarian sciences. The activities of the youth, their moral-ethical competencies, and their attitudes toward values are continuously analyzed in different political periods and cultural-educational events. Developing models of social, economic, and political activity based on the current state of the intellectual potential of the youth is one of the urgent issues in the social-humanitarian sciences. The active involvement of young people with high

intellectual and moral potential in specific areas, directing them within the framework of the law, and managing and controlling their activities align with the main directions of Uzbekistan's development strategy. Currently, the concept of "economic man" is being introduced in science, and discussions on its social-philosophical issues are being raised. The conclusion that "human behavior based on existing rules is the manifestation of various opportunities" suggests that youth's economic activity is viewed as an opportunity.

In our opinion, in determining the immanent characteristics of moral factors in economically activating the youth, the following should be considered: firstly, improving the system of material and moral incentives for youth activity in small business, private entrepreneurship, and the social sector through various legal sources; secondly, ensuring the effectiveness of employment and socio-ethical mobility measures for the youth; thirdly, deepening reforms in the continuous education system and improving the professional competence of young specialists and workers; fourthly, enhancing the functional activities of authorities that strengthen and ensure the youth's moral environment and physical health; fifthly, achieving the prioritization of infrastructure activities in the economic field and harmonizing the youth's aspiration for material and moral wealth.

In the economic life of society, institutional and functional changes are directing humans toward creativity and innovation, leading to the formation of the innovative aesthetic form of economic activity and theoretical types of activity. The intensification of youth activity is manifested in the fields of production, services, and tourism as innovations. The human desire to create cultural-aesthetic values has historically stemmed from economic activity, production, or social relationships, based on real-life needs. These needs have defined the character and essence of human economic activity, which is why peoples in the West have created innovative economies and economic-aesthetic wealth that starkly differ from those in the East. However, it should not be forgotten that underlying economic-aesthetic values are also human artistic-aesthetic, moral, and spiritual needs.

The effective application of innovative technologies and developments in improving the well-being of our people, improving legislation regulating relations between authors and clients, enhancing the regulatory-legal base, establishing a single authorized body for innovation and innovation infrastructure, and developing strategies for action are among the main priorities of Uzbekistan's national development agenda. As Shavkat Mirziyoyev

stated: "Creating an innovation environment in our people's worldview is our most important task. Without innovation, there will be no competition or development in any sector. If we do not promote changes in this area among our people, if we do not instill new skills, we will not be able to keep pace with the unprecedented achievements of science and technology in this era."

As noted, in the context of the growing globalization of the world economy, it is essential to improve the mechanisms of state support for national innovative scientific-technical activity, promote innovative technologies in agriculture, and formulate innovative strategies in various sectors of the economy, which should be at the center of attention of scholars and lawmakers.

In the context of structural and functional restructuring of the economy, the transition to market relations in the fields of labor and employment has created a new principle in social-labor relations. This is particularly evident in the youth sector, as youth, due to their socio-psychological characteristics, are not yet ready for the conditions of the modern labor market. When first entering the labor market, the youth have unrealistic perceptions about their future professions and career prospects, and in conditions where employment is impossible, they face complex situations (anxiety, depression, leading to a sense of guilt) during their initial steps in the labor market.

In an innovative economy, the real market that forms is the market for innovations. As specialists, youth are subjects who constantly replenish the labor market as hired workers. Today, the youth workforce is expanding, and these youth contribute to the market with their innovative developments. These fairs serve as exhibitions of production technologies and the latest scientific achievements. Recently, the "IV Republican Fair of Innovative Ideas, Technologies, and Projects" has led to the signing of approximately 400 contracts and memoranda worth nearly 10 billion Uzbek soums for the introduction of prospective developments created by our country's scientists and specialists.

CONCLUSION

It is important to note that in recent years, the number of youth engaging in various initiatives in science, education, production, entrepreneurship, and other fields is increasing. The economic activity of the youth today is characterized by the integration of real economic profitability, value, and other market concepts with aesthetic knowledge. In the context of an innovative economy, the aestheticization of economic activity is evident, as seen in a recent competition where only the automotive industry was covered, and issues of

aesthetic culture, ecological knowledge, and security were discussed. The result is the growing importance of aesthetic factors in the relationship between producers and consumers.

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